

1 *Harmonize rules for digital sequence information benefit-sharing across UN frameworks*

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 DNA sequencing revolutionized and digitalized the life sciences over the past few decades,
11 but the international legal frameworks governing genetic resources focused on physical
12 samples and paper permits. However, parallel negotiations under the UN Convention on
13 Biological Diversity, World Health Organization, Food and Agriculture Organization, and the
14 UN Convention of the Law of the Seas are now developing new rules to govern genetic data,
15 known as digital sequence information (DSI). A key challenge is to ensure these emerging
16 legal frameworks are harmonized across these UN fora so that scientists can continue to use
17 the full global DSI dataset without bureaucratic hurdles and unintended consequences. We
18 propose models for a harmonized DSI multilateral mechanism that would continue to allow
19 open access to DSI, database interoperability and ensure the accumulation of benefit sharing
20 from the use of DSI across the relevant UN fora.

21

22 **Introduction**

23 Steven Spielberg's *Life on Our Planet* begins with LUCA – the last universal common
24 ancestor – a humbling reminder that all life shares a common origin, a universal code. This
25 universality has fundamental implications for life scientists. With the decoding of DNA, the
26 molecular blueprint for life, open infrastructures like public DNA sequence databases have
27 become repositories for data from all life forms, from the microscopic to the macroscopic.
28 Due to the universal nature of the DNA code, an interconnected, global dataset with maximal
29 biological coverage became indispensable for understanding the fundamental biological
30 processes that make life possible.

31

32 While scientists shared genetic data (or digital sequence information, DSI) from across the
33 tree of life over the past four decades, laws on access to and utilization of (physical)
34 biological resources were also developed. The 1992 UN Convention on Biological Diversity

35 (CBD) underscored that countries have sovereign rights over their non-human biological
36 resources and aimed to promote the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the
37 utilization of genetic resources (GR). In practical terms, countries were empowered to make
38 national laws governing physical access to their genetic resources, to ensure benefits were
39 returned to the provider country. In 2010, the CBD's Nagoya Protocol created a legally
40 binding instrument where each country may (but not must) establish conditions of use of its
41 genetic resources and require users to share back with the provider country any monetary or
42 non-monetary benefits that arise from the utilization of those resources.

43

44 Benefit sharing systems are also found in other UN fora such as the Food and Agriculture
45 Organization's International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture
46 (ITPGRFA), the World Health Organization's (WHO) Pandemic Influenza Preparedness
47 (PIP) Framework and the under-negotiation Pandemic Agreement (WHO CA+), and the
48 recently adopted agreement under the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea on the
49 conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national
50 jurisdiction (BBNJ) treaty. Until recently, these agreements mainly focused on access to
51 physical biological material.

52

53 The political realization that access and benefit-sharing (ABS) rules developed decades ago
54 for access to physical genetic resources are often disconnected from access and use of open
55 biological sequence data has placed the world of open data and its freely accessible global
56 archive on a collision course with these UN fora. While some countries have issued national
57 laws on the use of DSI¹, use of open DSI has been unregulated at the international level.

58 However, countries are now actively negotiating multilateral rules on how to share monetary
59 and non-monetary benefits from the use of DSI in four relevant UN fora (i.e. CBD,
60 ITPGRFA, WHO CA+ and BBNJ).

61

62 The development of these UN agreements, for the past 40 years, was driven by sectoral
63 interests over different time points and has led to a patchwork of international laws and
64 national implementing measures that create a labyrinth of rules and conditions for researchers
65 to understand. While these UN fora are under no obligation to make rules that are cross-
66 compatible for users of the global DSI archive, we currently have an opportunity for
67 harmonization and futureproofing that we did not have in the past. We believe the
68 relationship between the new DSI benefit sharing systems being developed under the four

69 UN fora can be structured to increase benefit sharing and maintain open access and
70 interoperability of DSI databases.

71

72 **Why do users of DSI need integrated access across biologically diverse datasets?**

73 The power of DSI fully unfolds when comparison with all other sequences is possible. A
74 single DNA or amino acid sequence is of little use and must be annotated and analyzed for
75 similarities and differences to thousands of other sequences to fully exploit its scientific
76 value, complemented by hands-on laboratory work. Research is inherently interdisciplinary
77 and collaborative across sub-disciplines and sectors. Researchers are interested in natural
78 relationships, rather than man-made divisions of the various UN fora, to answer critical
79 scientific questions.

80

81 Open public DSI databases, such as the International Nucleotide Sequence Database
82 Collaboration (INSDC), were built on these principles to facilitate, enable and maintain
83 interoperability of data across domains of life to foster efficient and impactful analyses. The
84 INSDC contains DSI generated from biological samples from nearly every existing
85 environment across the planet. The data are “mixed up” together (Figure 1) and available
86 under the same open access conditions².

87

88 If we assigned the data currently available in INSDC according to the four relevant UN
89 agreements (assuming universal ratification and implementation and ignoring temporal
90 scope) the greatest portion of the INSDC dataset comes from organisms within scope of the
91 CBD and resulting national legislation (56%), followed by ITPGRFA crops (10%), WHO-
92 relevant potentially-pandemic-causing pathogens (3%), and <1% to BBNJ (Figure 1, see
93 supplement material for methodology). Note that several industrialized countries do not
94 require benefit sharing from the use of their genetic resources, but for the sake of simplicity,
95 the data is included under the CBD scope. The “out of scope” category accounts for 11% and
96 encompasses model organisms, synthetic sequences and human data. The “patents” category
97 (19%) includes sequence reference material submitted as part of the patent application to
98 ensure reproducibility of an invention under the World Intellectual Property Organization
99 system (WIPO Standard 26). (WIPO agreed in May 2024 to require disclosure of country of
100 origin for genetic resources and/or traditional knowledge in patent applications, however, a
101 decision on whether this will could apply for DSI will be revisited in four years.)

102

103 **Figure 1. DSI is “mixed together” in a global dataset regardless of UN fora.** Left side of
 104 the diagram: taxonomic distribution across 8 phylogenetic groups organized in a cladogram
 105 based on their phylogeny relative to the last universal common ancestor, LUCA and 2 groups
 106 without taxonomic information. “Virus” and “Other eukaryota” are non-monophyletic
 107 groups. The dashed and faded line connecting viruses to LUCA indicates uncertainties in the
 108 phylogenetic relationship of the group. The thickness of the lines connecting the two sides of
 109 the diagram is proportional to the number of sequences assigned to each taxonomic category
 110 and UN fora. Right side of the diagram: assignment of sequences to relevant UN fora based
 111 on absolute number of sequence entries in the database. DSI are color-coded indicating
 112 whether a country tag was explicitly indicated in the ENA metadata of each individual entry
 113 (green) as country of origin or if the tag was missing (red). In parentheses the percentage
 114 relative to the total dataset.

115

116 Figure 1 demonstrates why harmonization is a significant issue for DSI users (i.e. scientists).
 117 Users might be interested in a specific group of animals or bacteria or a specific function like
 118 photosynthesis or cell signaling. To explore those topics requires use of DSI from many fora

119 and, in the future, compliance with all international rules on DSI. If those rules are
 120 complicated or unharmonized, that scientific work will be hindered.

121
 122 To demonstrate the integrative manner of DSI analysis needed to address urgent scientific
 123 and societal questions, we have generated public health, food security and sustainable use
 124 case studies based on published literature that show how and why DSI users need integrated
 125 access to DSI from various UN fora (Box 1). These case studies reflect the way research is
 126 conducted, providing valuable lessons for policymakers to take into consideration moving
 127 forward in the negotiations.

128

HARMONIZATION CASE STUDIES based on published literature

<p>A. Using DSI to develop a vaccine (WHO CA+ & CBD/NP)</p>	<p>B. Emerging crop resistance to new biological and environmental threats (CBD/NP & IT-PGRFA)</p>	<p>C. DSI databases used to develop sustainable, eco-friendly, and efficient fabric detergents based on cold-active enzymes (CBD/NP & BBNJ DSI)</p>
<p>The development of a COVID-19 vaccine was a complex procedure dependent on global scientific collaboration and open access to DSI. Moderna’s patent US-10702600-B1: betacoronavirus mRNA vaccine³, filed in February 2020, describes an mRNA vaccine for respiratory viruses, particularly betacoronaviruses (the genera that includes SARS-CoV-2, which causes COVID-19). The patent draws on 176 publicly available (via INSDC) DSI from different respiratory viruses, from a large range of countries (e.g., Saudi Arabia, UK, UAE, Jordan, France, USA, Qatar, Thailand, Oman, China). It also discloses 96 new sequences, submitted to public DSI databases alongside the patent. Some are similar or identical to existing public sequences, others represent engineered or modified versions of sequences already referenced elsewhere in the patent document. Many are labelled as “Artificial Sequence” and have no country of origin. Not one SARS-CoV-2 sequence is listed in the patent. This large variety</p>	<p>An estimated 70% of wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>) produced around the world is used for human consumption and is an indispensable food source for one-third of the world’s population, especially as global populations continue to increase⁴. Although the ‘Green Revolution’ increased crop yields through breeding technologies, wheat crops are still susceptible to diseases. To date, investments in fungicides in Europe account for ~€1.3 billion, 70% towards a single pathogen, <i>Zyloseptoria tritici</i>⁵, which causes Septoria tritici Blotch (STB) disease. As a result of widespread fungicide application, resistant <i>Z. tritici</i> strains have recently evolved. A French study⁶ investigated microbial communities of wheat varieties, two susceptible to STB and one resistant strain, over a growing season. Using specialized domain-specific (not organism specific) open access DSI databases (e.g., SILVA⁷, UNITE⁸), researchers identified and compared fungal and bacterial communities in infected and healthy wheat to infer whether specific fungal/bacterial composition could act as beneficial biocontrol against <i>Z. tritici</i>. While <i>Z. tritici</i> was present in all samples, it showed higher abundance in unhealthy leaves and was less abundant on the</p>	<p>The production of efficient industrial enzymes, needed for waste reduction, energy efficiency, and even mitigation of greenhouse gases, is a central goal of the white biotechnology sector. Cold-active enzymes, from microorganisms living in temperature ranges of -2 to 20°C can be found in a variety of environments, including deserts, mountains, wetlands, polar regions, and the deep-sea. These enzymes provide similar functionality at lower temperatures compared to their high-temperature counterparts,</p> <p>In 2018⁹ a novel α-amylase (amy175) was characterized from a newly isolated Antarctic Sea ice bacterium (M175). The bacterial species identity was determined by comparing 16S rDNA gene sequences from INSDC and conducting phylogenetic analysis. The new species demonstrated high levels of similarity to 15 known species of <i>Pseudoalteromonas</i>, a species with widespread global distribution. Furthermore, the comparison of amy175 to 27 selected amylases DSI sequences</p>

<p>of sequences, including the omission of the specific SARS-CoV-2 sequences, demonstrates that Moderna was free to decide which sequences to include in the patent document, as long as they fulfilled the requirements for reproducibility. No single sequence was vital to its work. Interestingly, the mRNA present in the vaccine is only 70% identical to any natural SARS-CoV-2 found in the INSDC².</p>	<p>variety that carried a known fungal resistance gene (i.e. Stb16q). The results showed that sampling date, wheat variety and health of the leaves had significant effects on the fungal and bacterial communities. The DSI used in this study was from crop genetic resources regulated under the ITPGRFA's multilateral system, and from weeds, fungal, and bacteria genetic resources regulated under national measures implementing the CBD/NP.</p>	<p>confirmed that amy175 had highly conserved regions associate to amylase activity. While those 27 sequences provided valuable information to classify enzymatic activity none had country of origin information. The comparison of new DSI to previously available DSI in public databases is a critical tool for characterizing genetic material from novel organisms.</p>
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129

130 **Box 1.** Human health (A), Food security (B) and Sustainability (C) case studies from
131 published literature and how the use of DSI in each case study uses DSI from more than one
132 UN fora to answer scientific questions.

133

134 ***Lesson #1: Ensure DSI interoperability.***

135 If DSI access or database interoperability is impeded, it will undermine research innovation
136 rather than supporting and enabling it. For example, under the WHO CA+ discussions,
137 negotiators have looked at the PIP Framework and have discussed a similar model for the
138 new treaty. Influenza DSI and, more recently, SARS-CoV-2 DSI, have often been deposited
139 in the Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data (GISAID) database, which curates and
140 regulates access to these data. GISAID provides free-of-charge access to registered and
141 verified accounts. In exchange, users must agree to a data access agreement including to
142 acknowledge the submitting scientist when re-using data in a publication. Importantly, the
143 agreement prohibits GISAID from integrating and sharing its data with fully open databases,
144 such as INSDC (although the original data providers may share their data outside of
145 GISAID). The vaccine development case study (Box 1A) would not have been possible if the
146 only legally-certain source of viral DSI was in GISAID. Vaccine development requires
147 exploring all of viral biodiversity which is only available in the INSDC. It also requires the
148 integration of DSI with other biological protein sequence data and structures for vaccine
149 targets (epitopes) and the selected target's variation and molecular structure. DSI is combined
150 with chemical and enzymatic knowledge to increase stability and ensure proper folding. To
151 develop pandemic-responsive research and products, DSI needs to be integrated with many
152 types of viral DSI (and the respective databases that house these data) including human data
153 (to understand host-pathogen relationships), protein structure data (to move towards vaccine

154 development), or clinical and imaging data (for new ideas on disease progression). A single,
155 closed, non-interoperable database will not enable pandemic preparedness.

156

157 ***Lesson #2: Make benefit-sharing rules as similar as possible***

158 Most users will not know which UN fora the DSI they are using could belong to because
159 research questions are driven by a need to understand biological processes and not based on
160 the origin of DSI (geographical or legal provenance). If each UN forum develops its ‘own
161 DSI rules’, for example, on when, how, or whether to report or share benefits, then users will
162 need to track and trace the use of thousands of sequences used and engage with many
163 different platforms and administrative activities. However, if similar triggers for aggregate
164 DSI benefit sharing could be established in all UN fora, this would minimize the risk of
165 avoidance, incentivize and encourage compliance, and obviate the need to track and trace ¹⁰.

166

167 ***Lesson #3: Only harmonized DSI benefit-sharing rules will capture benefits from artificial***
168 ***DSI.***

169 With synthetic biology advancements, a dis-harmonized approach to DSI benefit-sharing
170 could incentivize DSI mechanism avoidance by synthesizing new sequences that cannot be
171 traced back to a geographical or legal provenance. Either doing this through codon
172 optimization or artificial intelligence (AI), it would be nearly impossible to trace back to the
173 original nature-based DSI because the new synthetic sequence would be quite different. For
174 example, for the sustainability case study (Box 1C), the next step in biotech development of
175 this cold-tolerant enzyme is to further synthesize and optimize the enzymatic properties. For-
176 profit entities will create consensus sequences to take the most common (genetically
177 conserved) amino acid at every position in the enzyme and create new, synthetic enzymes.
178 Synthetic sequences are human-made products that pool DSI derived from genetic resources
179 regulated under multiple fora. Thus, they cannot be tracked back to a single country or
180 jurisdiction of origin. A similar issue would arise for the vaccine case study (Box 1A), where
181 the final sequence used in the vaccine was only 70% similar to any natural sequence
182 deposited in the database. With harmonization across all relevant fora, all rules and roads can
183 convergently lead to DSI benefit-sharing, ideally aggregated across use of any and all DSI, no
184 matter how novel or man-made DSI might become.

185

186 **Options for “harmonious” DSI benefit sharing rules across UN fora**

187 As demonstrated above, to maximize the societal value of DSI, it must be made available in
188 the most integrated and interconnected way possible across all species and jurisdictions.
189 While the international rules on DSI benefit-sharing are all still under negotiation, the risk of
190 fragmentation is inevitable if policymakers assume DSI and its outcomes can be neatly
191 separated into siloes. But, what can policymakers do to create an enabling environment? Here
192 we present various “house models” where the house is a placeholder for the concept of DSI
193 benefit-sharing and not database infrastructures. Doors indicate triggers in which new
194 monetary benefits will be required but are not intended to imply a paywall (or a closed
195 access) approach to DSI benefit-sharing as these would severely limit benefit-sharing^{10,11}.
196 Windows indicate how the monetary benefits will be delivered to the relevant UN fora.

197

198 **Option 1: One house with one door and four windows**

199 If one were to design a monetary benefit sharing system for DSI from scratch, a single global
200 fund that collected benefits from any type of use of DSI would be a natural choice. In option
201 1 (Figure 2A), all four UN fora would adopt identical triggers for payment and soft law
202 norms for DSI governance. All payments by all users would be made to a single existing
203 global fund (1 door) such as the Global Biodiversity Framework fund (or another appropriate
204 global facility), which would distribute funds (through four windows) to the UN instruments
205 for further disbursement according to their respective governance procedures. Distribution
206 from the global fund to each of the four UN fora could be proportional to the payments made
207 by users in the relevant sectors or informed by the quantity of respective DSI available in
208 open access databases (Figure 1). However, this option is politically difficult as it requires all
209 four UN fora to adopt identical benefit sharing conditions and the use of one single global
210 fund. The ITPGRFA, for example, already has a multilateral ABS system, which provides a
211 useful basis upon which to ‘layer’ obligations for DSI benefit sharing, thus migrating to a
212 CBD-led DSI benefit-sharing process is not particularly attractive. The WHO pathogen
213 Access and Benefit Sharing System will likely keep monetary benefits within the WHO
214 system to fund pandemic prevention and preparedness efforts. However, for BBNJ DSI,
215 because it is a very small dataset (less than 1%), a not-yet-established mechanism, and
216 thematically focused on biodiversity, it is easier to imagine it could join forces *a priori* with
217 the CBD multilateral mechanism.

218

219 **Option 2: One house, four doors and four windows**

220 For option 2 (Figure 2B), each fora would have separate benefit sharing funds, receiving
 221 payments directly from users (through separate doors), and disbursing funds according to
 222 priorities established by the fora’s governance mechanisms (through four windows). In this
 223 model, a benefit sharing payment made through any door to any of the four instruments
 224 would fulfill benefit-sharing obligations in all of the others and ensure simplicity and
 225 freedom to operate. Similarly, non-monetary benefits shared and reported in a global
 226 clearinghouse would fulfill obligations in all of the others.

227
 228 Under option 2, the four UN fora do not need identical benefit sharing triggers, but they do
 229 all need to require payments in a similar way (e.g., a proportion of aggregate sales of
 230 products at the end of value chains). They also need to reciprocally recognize that benefit-
 231 sharing payments under any of the other four fora qualifies users to access all DSI without
 232 needing to calculate the proportion of DSI from different biota that were used throughout the
 233 research and development process. For example, the sale of seeds of a new pest resistant
 234 Annex 1 plant variety would trigger payments to only the ITPGRFA benefit-sharing fund,
 235 even if the DSI of pathogens were used as part of the research to develop the variety (Figure
 236 3A). Conversely, the sale of a new biocontrol agent, e.g. a soil bacterium, which required
 237 using DSI from ITPGRFA Annex 1 crops, would trigger benefit sharing payments (only) to
 238 the CBD fund (Figure 3B).

239

240
 241 **Figure 2.** Two proposed models for harmonization between UN fora. A) Option 1 - One
 242 house with one door and four windows. B) Option 2 - One house with four doors and four
 243 windows. Inside the house lies the open database ecosystem with the DSI of relevance to all
 244 different UN fora without jurisdictional sub-division. Doors indicate trigger points for

245 monetary benefits and windows indicate how the monetary benefits will be delivered to the
 246 relevant UN fora. The house represents the DSI benefit-sharing mechanism and not database
 247 infrastructures.
 248

249
 250

251 **Figure 3.** Flowcharts of two possible scenarios for benefit-sharing distribution under Option
 252 2. Scenario A: development of a new variety of an ITPGRFA Annex I plant that is resistant
 253 to a fungus that falls under the CBD. Although DSI of both the Annex I plant and the CBD-
 254 relevant fungi have been used, the DSI-related benefits resulting from the use of the new
 255 plant variety will stream to the ITPGRFA fund. In scenario B: identification of a bacterial
 256 strain in soil that falls under the scope of the CBD that promotes the growth of an ITPGRFA
 257 Annex I plant under stress conditions. Although DSI of both the bacterium and the plant have
 258 been instrumental to the discovery, the DSI-related benefits generated by the use of the
 259 bacteria strain will stream to the CBD fund. DSI = Digital Sequence Information, GR =
 260 physical Genetic Resource. Images generated with BioRender.com

261

262 For both options, users would continue to have open access to all publicly available DSI as
 263 long as they complied with benefit-sharing requirements and relevant monetary triggers to
 264 any (one) of the four UN fora. Both options would ensure open, integrated access to all public
 265 DSI; simplicity and legal certainty for users; no incentives for forum shopping between
 266 systems and no need for tracing/tracking from which fora the used DSI came from. It would
 267 also allow for benefit-sharing from the use of artificial sequences (i.e. produced by consensus
 268 sequence or increasingly AI) because origin would not be the determining factor for payment.
 269 The simplicity of either option for harmonization would be lost if one or more of the UN fora
 270 adopts a benefit sharing formula that involve tracking the proportional contribution of
 271 different DSI to the development of products. Under a dis-harmonized system, claims for
 272 benefit sharing from one UN fora or one country to a sequence that is only partially (X %)

273 similar to a natural one would be difficult to make. If there is no harmonization, users of DSI
274 could find or create sequences with fewer benefit-sharing obligations.

275

276 **Conclusions**

277 A harmonized multilateral system for DSI should have clear and simple standardized
278 conditions across fora for the use of all publicly available DSI. These would incentivize users
279 to comply with obligations if legal certainty and clarity is ensured. For the research
280 community, an extraordinarily important ‘whole’ must be preserved, nurtured, and expanded
281 by ensuring DSI is open access, interoperable, and universally accessible. Options 1 and 2
282 demonstrate that it is possible to develop new benefit sharing rules for DSI that build on the
283 institutional infrastructures of the CBD, Plant Treaty, WHO and BBNJ without dividing the
284 governance of the global DSI data set between sectoral lines.

285

286 **Recommendations to enable DSI harmonization**

- 287 1. *The creation of an inter-fora expert advisory board* that supports the process to
288 develop harmonized rules between the four UN fora so that benefit sharing
289 contributions in one system can be recognized in the other three. If users benefit-
290 sharing obligations arise under just one system, they should nonetheless have access
291 to the entire global DSI dataset. Engaging with a broad range of stakeholders
292 (policymakers, academia, database managers, private sector and indigenous peoples
293 and local communities) through informal dialogue and inter-forum discussion will
294 enrich the decision-making process and potential outcomes¹². Users of DSI are often
295 the ones directly impacted by the rules and restrictions imposed by these international
296 frameworks and cannot be isolated from the decision-making process on benefit-
297 sharing. Active engagement from the academic sector during the development of the
298 DSI multilateral mechanism has been essential to inform the process and provide
299 empirical evidence on how DSI data is created, used, and shared. It is critically
300 important that negotiators consider the broader picture of how all four agreements can
301 work together, in mutually supportive ways, to contribute to a whole greater than the
302 sum of the four parts.
- 303 2. *Learn how harmonization has been achieved in other UN processes.* Other global
304 decision-making bodies have harmonized their procedures across multiple fora (e.g.,
305 customs export control, international air transport association, weather data and model
306 forecasting, etc.) and can serve as examples of how this result can be achieved,

307 especially with regards to scientific and technical issues. We suggest that the CBD
308 commission a study on how harmonization in other UN processes has been achieved
309 in the past and how those processes can be managed to reach harmonization. This can
310 provide lessons for a DSI inter-foa system. This could be a first step in working
311 together towards a common goal.

312 3. Signal to other fora the desire to work together on DSI. There are simple signals
313 negotiators can send to indicate the intent that rules on benefit-sharing they create in
314 one forum to integratively work with rules in the other fora. For example, using the
315 same (or lack thereof) definition for DSI, sufficiently similar trigger points for when
316 benefits should be shared, textual reference and citations of other instruments, all can
317 work together to signal to users and lawyers alike that the DSI rules are intended to
318 integrate across the scientific DSI ecosystem rather than to fragment it.

319 4. Develop a comprehensive global DSI capacity-building and non-monetary benefit-
320 sharing plan. There remain significant gaps in global capacities to produce and use
321 DSI. All four UN fora indicate their intention to invest in DSI-related capacity
322 strengthening but few efforts have been made to define how and what that would be,
323 and no efforts have been made to develop an ambitious, global plan to truly impact
324 inequalities in DSI use. For example, regional centers of excellence with different
325 sectoral focuses (health, agriculture, bioeconomy, conservation) could each be led by
326 different fora but share core features such as training, infrastructure development,
327 cloud services, in cross-cutting areas. A harmonized, global DSI capacity building
328 strategy that would complement efforts and integrate with existing portals such as
329 UNESCO's The World Academy of Sciences, could create concrete, impactful
330 actions on DSI outcomes. For non-monetary benefits, a harmonized approach to
331 reporting and monitoring DSI non-monetary benefits across all UN fora would be
332 vastly simpler than multiple rules, mechanisms and portals.

333

334 Harmonization among the different frameworks will undoubtedly be challenging, as each
335 framework serves a different purpose, including the conservation and sustainable use of
336 biodiversity (CBD/NP/BBNJ), disease detection, prevention, and eradication (PIP, WHO
337 CA+), and food security (IPTGRFA). Each framework has different decision-making
338 processes, compliance measures, and designated national negotiators (often from different
339 government offices or ministries) with mandates that may not overlap or even compete for
340 budgets and political prioritization. However, if benefit-sharing from DSI for each of these

341 fora is conceived of separately rather than in an interlinked global context, a real risk exists
342 that the value of these data will decrease due to legal uncertainty and bureaucratic burden.
343 Ironically, the new DSI system that aims to maximize benefits would instead reduce the
344 benefits being created.

345

346 Research is the primary pathway through which benefits from DSI are realized. Benefits
347 (monetary and non-monetary) come in a range of forms, such as generating new knowledge
348 and the development of scientific innovations. An opportunity to develop a harmonized
349 mechanism(s) for the use of DSI that is compatible with scientific practices and DSI database
350 structures, while at the same time maximizing benefits shared from the use of DSI to help
351 achieve the objective of individual frameworks, is now before us.

352

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